

An Abnormal Acid-Base Reaction: Displacement of a Strong Acid (or Base) by a Weak Acid (or Base)

SANTI R. PALIT and ARINDAM CHAUDHURI

Department of Physical Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur, Calcutta-32

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Contrary to the common notion that a strong acid can not be displaced from its salt by a weak acid, a number of observations in organic solvents are reported herein where the opposite takes place. Similarly, cases of displacement of a strong base by a weak base in organic solvents have been reported. Hard-soft-acid-base (HSAB) principle can probably take into account the course of such abnormal reactions; however an inherent difficulty due to such striking difference between aqueous and non-aqueous systems is pointed out.

ONE of the authors proposed a dye interaction technique^{1,2} for determination of end group of polymers in one type of which a colourless dye base, say a triphenylmethane dye base, was reacted in benzene with an acid end group of a polymer to form the coloured dye salt as represented below:

Colourless Dye base (Carbinol base)	Polymer with sulphonic acid end group	Coloured Dye salt
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It was however observed that not only acid end groups but also salt end groups often react in the same direction producing coloured dye salt evidently according to the equation

Eqn. (2) is a very unexpected reaction because here a weak dye base is displacing the strongest base sodium hydroxide. It now appears that such abnormal behaviour is very common in benzene and many other organic solvents and the present paper is meant to draw attention to a few typical examples of this type of reaction as also its counterpart where a weak acid displaces a strong acid.

Experimental

Displacement of a Strong Base by a Weak Dye Base: Almost any basic dye can be used for the purpose. Preparation of the dye base is most conveniently done by dissolving the dye in a buffer of pH 10-11 and extracting with benzene, a technique introduced by Palit^{1,2}. A typical process for preparation of the stock solution of the dye base is as follows.

About 5 mg of the basic dye is dissolved in 10 ml of a phosphate or carbonate buffer of pH about 10 and is extracted with a total volume of 50 ml of benzene in two successive extractions. The colourless or yellow (in some cases, brown) benzene extract is kept over solid NaOH pellets. To determine the dye concentration, this solution is extracted with a dilute acid solution and the dye concentration is determined colorimetrically. This extract is found to contain practically the whole of the dye originally taken. This stock solution is diluted with dry benzene to the desired concentration when necessary.

A polymer sample is prepared by polymerising an aqueous solution (1%) of methyl methacrylate under nitrogen using persulphate-meta bisulphite as redox initiator³. The polymer contains both SO_3Na and SO_2Na end group. The amount of end group is determined by the dye partition technique⁴ and a benzene solution of the polymer (after the usual purification) of known end group concentration is prepared as a stock solution.

On mixing the polymer sulphate-sulphonate solution with the dye extract, the cationic colour of the dye develops. The rate ranges from quite fast to quite slow. Most dyes respond fairly well, a notable exception being crystal violet. The equilibrium conversion at room temperature (near 30°) of some basic dyes whose benzene extract is colourless, both the polymer and the dye being at about 10^{-4} molar concentration, is presented in Table 1. All attempts to obtain the usual equilibrium constant based on equation (2) failed. It would be seen from the table that Auramine OS and Astrazon violet are the most reactive. This may be related to their base strength; however no data are available on base strength of carbinol bases to test this point.

A simple consequence of equation (2) is that if the liberated alkali could be removed by some means, the reaction would go more towards the right *i.e.*, more colour would be developed. This is easily seen to be true by adding a small quantity of a benzene-insoluble acid *viz.*, solid hydrated oxalic acid (or tartaric acid or citric acid) or an ion-exchange resin (acid form) to the system; the colour is seen to intensify very strongly sometimes at a slow rate to practically 100% conversion. This opens up the possibility of using almost any basic dye, instead of only a few such dyes which are empirically found to have the equilibrium point close to almost 100% conversion for the dye interaction method of end group determination^{1,2} or for that matter, for estimation of any benzene-soluble salt, anionic detergent, etc. This observation also raises the possibility of using the same calibration curve for all such ionic polymers or other benzene-soluble ionic compounds using the same dye. This analytical application will be dealt with in a separate publication.

Displacement of a Strong Acid by a Weak Acid: Not only a strong base is displaced by a weak base in benzene as discussed in the previous section but also its counterpart *i.e.*, displacement of a strong acid by a weak acid is also frequently possible in benzene. A typical reaction is as follows:

One of the authors proposed this reaction for detection of ammonium (including quaternary ammonium) end group in polymers^{1,2}. Evidently the weak organic acid is displacing the strong mineral acid in benzene medium to a considerable extent, an impossible feat in aqueous medium. Even the extremely weak phenolic acid can replace strong inorganic acids in the above type of reaction. This is easily observed if say, a nitrophenol or an ester of the above type of dyes is taken as shown by the following equations

Conversion data for a few eosin type dyes are presented in Table 1. It should be noted how slight change of structure affects the power of the dye in this respect (compare Erythrosin J and Erythrosin pur.).

Not only polymeric ammonium end groups^{1,2} but also ordinary quaternary ammonium salts (tetrabutyl ammonium chloride) were observed by Steigman and Lorenz⁵ to cause very slow intensification of colour of bromophthalein magenta in benzene which was strongly catalysed by organic bases. These authors thought that the main reaction was between the phenolic dye and the base (either the added base or the alkali from glass wall) followed by double decomposition without realising this to be a case of displacement of a strong acid by a weak

TABLE 1

Dye	Percent Conversion*	Colour change from colourless to—
Dye concentration $\approx 10^{-4}(M)$ Basic Dyes $\sim\text{SO}_3\text{Na}$ Concentration $\approx 10^{-4}(M)$		
1. Astrazon rosa	34.0	Rose
2. Methyl violet	8.7	Violet
3. Astrazon violet	57.9	deep pinkish red
4. Astrazon neufuchsin	20.2	Magenta
5. Auramine OS	49.8	Yellow
Dye concentration $\approx 10^{-4}(M)$ Acid Dyes Quaternary Salt Concentration $\approx 10^{-3}(M)$		
1. Eosin H8G	53.93	Pinkish greenish yellow fluorescence
2. Erythrosin J	44.6	"
3. Erythrosin 6G	23.2	"
4. Erythrosin pur	7.6	"
5. Rose bengal	21.6	Pink

* Determined with the help of Hilger UV-Spectrophotometer.

one. As a matter of fact, Davis⁶ the pioneer worker in studying the reaction of the phenolic dye bromophthalein magenta with base in benzene prepared the quaternary ammonium salt by reaction between the quaternary ammonium hydroxide and the dye instead of attempting by a path of the type of eqn. (4) or (5). The apparent infeasibility must have discouraged these workers to explore such a possibility. Guhaniyogi *et al.*⁷ of our laboratory has studied spectroscopically a reaction of the type shown in eqn. (5) between the ethyl ester of eosin and tetrabutyl ammonium chloride in benzene.

It follows from the equilibrium shown in eqns. (3), (4) and (5) that the reaction should be capable of being pushed forward if the acid formed (here HCl) can be removed from the system. This, we have found, can be easily done by adding solid NaOH or KOH or an ion-exchange resin (basic form) to the system. We have found this to be true for all eosin dyes so far tested, *viz.*, eosin, rose bengal, etc. Even the extremely sluggish dye fluorescein

which is too sluggish to produce a colour even with a free organic base in benzene gives positive colour reaction as above on addition of NaOH pellets. The possibility of analytical application of the above observation is evidently manifold and will be examined in a separate publication.

Other Solvents: Benzene is not the only solvent where such abnormal reactions take place. Most water-immiscible organic solvents such as hydrocarbons, chlorinated hydrocarbons, nitrobenzene, etc. act as the medium for such reactions with more or less ease depending on the system. Even with suitable dyes (i.e., a dye base which does not show its ionic colour in alcohol) reactions of the type shown in equation (2) takes place in alcohol with ease. It has not been possible to try water as solvent due to solubility considerations.

Theory: It is evident that the results are in conflict with the well-accepted notion of strength of acids. It may be thought that it is a solvent effect, the organic solvents reducing the strength of all acids and bases to a more or less common level, a kind of 'leveling effect' in reverse. However, dielectric constant does not appear to have a role, because these reactions are found to take place in a more or less equally facile way in a wide range of organic solvents as mentioned in the previous section.

Another explanation may be offered from the soft-hard—acid-base principle, the bulky anion preferring the bulky cation both being 'soft'⁸. However, it is then difficult to understand why HI is easily liberated by nitrophenols from quaternary iodides though iodide ion being highly polarisable is generally regarded as a highly soft base. May be, the aromatic phenolate ion is far more polarisable than the iodide ion. It would be interesting to see what happens if the quaternary ammonium salt (eqns. 3, 4 and 5) has a big polarisable organic anion. It appears that the usual notion of acid-base strength is of very restricted validity in displacement reactions in many organic solvents, a fact which has hitherto hardly received due recognition.

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